

Original Research

Corporate Contributions to Sustainable Development Goals in Bangladesh: A Comprehensive Analysis of DSE-30 Listed Companies

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Abstract

The paper aims to present how companies integrate Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into their reports, clarify corporate contributions to specific SDGs, and identify industries with significant SDGs engagement. Theoretical frameworks like legitimacy theory, stakeholder theory, and institutional theory suggest that companies report on SDGs to validate their activities in the eyes of stakeholders. Using content analysis with the PwC framework, this study examines DSE-30 listed companies in Bangladesh from 2017 to 2021. The study highlights that, among the selected companies, 62% of companies mentioned SDGs, with 41% actively prioritizing (focusing on specific goals) SDGs and 38% producing dedicated SDGs reports by 2021, which reflects a significant growth from previous years. Moreover, companies primarily focus on SDGs 8, SDGs 4, and SDGs 1, while SDGs 14 receives less attention due to fewer engagement opportunities. Financial institutions, banks, and food & allied sectors are prominent industry contributors, with average SDGs scores of 92%, 87%, and 85%, respectively, highlighting their vital role in promoting sustainable development in Bangladesh. This study urges regulators to focus on developing mechanisms to evaluate corporate contribution to SDGs, highlights the need for businesses to adopt sustainable practices, and serves as a key resource for stakeholders promoting sustainable development.

Keywords: Corporate Contributions, Corporate Social Responsibility Sustainability, SDGs reporting.

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Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), set by the UN in 2015 with a target date of 2030, address global challenges like poverty, inequality, and inclusive development (Erin & Bamigboye, 2022). The business sector plays a vital role in achieving these goals despite challenges in measuring individual contributions (Perello-Marín et al., 2022a). Increasingly, companies are reporting on SDGs-related efforts, focusing on areas such as climate change, water management, and working conditions, demonstrating growing corporate engagement with the SDGs (Mohin et al., 2018).

Saha & Jannat (2021) argued that organizations, regardless of their size or activities, can contribute to Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through their performance and reporting mechanisms. SDGs reporting offers numerous benefits. Detailing SDGs commitment enhances corporate social responsibility (CSR), and public perception can also be improved by portraying firms as socially and ecologically conscious (Erin et al., 2022). Companies in industrialized regions like China, Japan, and Europe are actively collaborating with their governments to support the achievement of SDGs, as noted by Threlfall et al. (2020), reflecting a growing global commitment to sustainability.

Bangladesh, one of the Next Eleven developing middle-income countries, recorded a GDP growth rate of 7.1%, exceeding that of India (7%), Pakistan (6.2%), Nepal (5.6%), and Bhutan (4.1%) in 2021 (World Bank Group, 2022). Bangladesh, as a UN member, adopted the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in 2001 and worked toward them for 15 years. By 2015, Bangladesh had reduced poverty from 56.7% to 24.8%, increased primary school enrollment to 81.3%, lowered maternal mortality by 47% between 2001 and 2013, and cut the child death rate by two-thirds while reducing gender gaps in education (Alam, 2016). These achievements reflect Bangladesh's successful development strategies and strong commitment to the UN's global agenda, resulting in significant socio-economic progress and a focus on sustainable development.

Since the UN announced the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2016, Bangladesh has integrated these goals into its economic plan with a target year of 2030. The government has adopted a "whole-of-society" approach to achieve key objectives, such as reducing the poverty rate to 9.7% and malnutrition to below 10%. According to Saha & Jannat (2021), the 'Citizen's Platform for SDGs, Bangladesh' has been instrumental in developing frameworks for SDGs implementation. They also noted that Bangladesh has embedded SDGs into its seventh five-year national plan, engaging local governments and various organizations. The financial sector, including companies listed on the Dhaka and Chittagong Stock Exchanges, is pivotal in advancing SDGs through stringent regulations and adherence to UN-issued rules, such as the UN Global Compact and the Sustainable Development Goals. Additionally, some listed companies actively address CSR issues such as poverty, education, and climate change, demonstrating a collaborative effort between the government and businesses toward global sustainability goals (Masud & Hossain, 2012 ; Masum et al., 2020; Raquiba & Ishak, 2020).

Evaluating the private sector's role in Bangladesh's pursuit of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is crucial, as government efforts alone may be insufficient. Though numerous studies have been found on corporate social responsibility and

sustainability reporting, SDGs reporting practices have been less explored academically. The study of Saha & Jannat (2021) hasn't focused on specific SDGs reporting by the selected firms. Besides, the study of Erin & Bamigboye (2022) provides insights on Nigerian companies, but the Bangladeshi companies aren't thoroughly explored yet. This research aims to address these gaps by investigating SDGs reporting trends among top-listed corporations in Bangladesh. The study will assess current reporting practices and provide insights into how the private sector contributes to the SDGs. By filling this research gap, the study will enhance understanding of private sector involvement in advancing the SDGs in Bangladesh. This study specifically focuses on attaining the following research objectives:

1. Analyzing how companies incorporate SDGs reporting into their corporate reports.
2. Examining the precise contributions of companies towards individual SDGs.
3. Evaluating the sector-specific contributions to each Sustainable Development Goals.

This study uses the PwC framework (Scott & McGill, 2018), "From Promise to Reality: Does Business Really Care About the SDGs?" to analyze SDGs reporting compliance. It focuses on firms in the DSE 30 index of the Dhaka Stock Exchange as of October 1, 2022, assuming these leading companies engage in more comprehensive reporting practices, including both voluntary and mandatory reports, compared to other organizations to promote their fame.

This research is structured into five parts, with the first portion as the introduction. The second section contains the literature review and theoretical framework. Section 03 provides a comprehensive overview of the research methodology. The findings are summarized in section 04, while conclusions are summarized in section 05.

Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

Legitimacy theory, as posited by Suchman (1995), argues that organizations must conform to social norms and expectations to successfully explore their business contexts. For companies to operate successfully, corporations must get legitimacy from society, which may be accomplished by transparently disclosing their activities that contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals and environmental preservation (Deegan, 2002). Enterprises provide non-financial information not only to capital market players but also to other non-financial stakeholders, thereby shaping their perceived legitimacy (Hummel & Szekely, 2022).

According to Freeman (1984), stakeholder theory argues that enterprises should be responsible to a wider range of stakeholders, not only those who are primarily concerned with or affected by the firm's financial goals. Every individual or group with a vested interest in the company, regardless of their affiliation, is entitled to receive information about financial, social, environmental, and governance matters (Erin & Bamigboye,

2022). To meet this responsibility, companies consistently generate and release SDGs reports, and sustainability reports, which provide stakeholders with valuable information on the company's initiatives in the economic, environmental, and social aspects of sustainable development.

Institutional theory posits that managers face pressure to adopt or modify various voluntary corporate reporting practices. Consequently, this pressure drives the adoption of socially and ecologically responsible practices, such as integrating environment-friendly measures in financial reporting. Institutions play a pivotal role in facilitating SDGs reporting within company reports. Pizzi et al. (2022) underscored the significance of early adoption of best practices, suggesting that late adopters should include SDGs in their reports to mitigate reputational concerns associated with a lack of non-financial information on SDGs. Whittingham et al. (2023) highlighted that the global emphasis on Sustainable Development Goals exerts normative pressure on firms, influencing both the content and structure of their reporting. A recent study confirms the concrete influence of normative pressure placed by Sustainable Development Goals on reporting practices. Evidence of the relationship between reporting SDGs direction and distinct governance characteristics is found in the research conducted by Bebbington & Unerman (2018) on the role of accounting in achieving Sustainable Development Goals, by Pizzi et al. (2021) on Italian businesses, and by Rosati & Faria (2019a) across 90 countries worldwide. The implementation of SDGs may prompt corporations to alter their sustainability reporting, driven by stakeholders' perceptions that increasingly view such reporting as an accepted and expected practice, particularly for large firms.

Literature Review

Sustainable Development, Sustainability Reporting, and SDGs

Sustainable development, as highlighted by Erin & Bamigboye (2022) and Rosati & Faria (2019b), requires balancing present economic growth with the preservation of resources for future generations. The concept now encompasses three key pillars: global social development, effective environmental and natural resource protection, and economic expansion, known as the "Triple Bottom Line" approach (Mohin et al., 2018; Nichita et al., 2020; Perello-Marin et al., 2022b; Rosati & Faria, 2019a, 2019b). Nechita et al. (2020) argue that true sustainability requires significant action across all three pillars, beyond merely disclosing environmental data. For ensuring sustainable development, the world leaders targeted to achieve 17 goals (called sustainable development goals) by 2030.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) significantly influence sustainability reporting, providing a framework for organizations to align their initiatives (Rosati & Faria, 2019a). Through sustainability reports, companies aim to boost brand value, enhance competitiveness, ensure transparency, and benchmark against peers (Herzig & Schaltegger, 2011). The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) is widely recognized for global sustainability reporting (Rosati & Faria, 2019a). In collaboration with the United Nations Global Compact (UNGC), GRI released "Integrating the Sustainable Development Goals into Corporate Reporting: A Practical Guide" (Kingo & Mohin, 2018; Mohin et al., 2018) to help companies incorporate SDGs reporting into their operations.

The PwC framework offers a four-step strategy for integrating Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into business practices (Erin & Bamigboye, 2022), advising companies to strategically assess the SDGs, particularly where they can have the most impact (Scott & McGill, 2019). It emphasizes setting specific targets aligned with key business areas. Biggeri et al. (2019) introduced the "integrated-sustainable development index (I-SDI)" to evaluate SDGs reporting at national and corporate levels, supporting the effectiveness of the PwC framework. Erin & Bamigboye (2022) applied this approach in African countries to assess SDGs disclosure, while Erin et al. (2022) extended it to Nigerian companies. Their findings revealed that only 10% of Nigeria's top companies mentioned the term SDGs in their annual reports, indicating gaps in SDGs disclosure in Africa. But research focusing on SDGs reporting is less explored in Bangladesh.

The Corporate Sector's Growing Interest in SDGs Reporting

Now Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are being incorporated by many organizations into their non-financial reporting to align with the 2030 Agenda (Threlfall et al., 2020). CEOs increasingly include SDGs in company reports to meet stakeholder demands (Curtó-Pagès et al., 2021). Rosati & Faria (2019a) found that 16% of 408 organizations addressed SDGs in their 2016 reports. Diaz-Sarachaga (2021) revealed that 36% of Spanish IBEX-35 index firms aligned with the 2030 Agenda, with only 11% actively contributing to SDGs and 28% monitoring and recording their precise contributions.

The KPMG Survey of Sustainability Reporting 2020 (Threlfall et al., 2020) revealed that a majority of the G-250 (largest companies globally based on sales) and N-100 (top 100 companies by revenue) integrated Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) into their corporate reporting. It marks a significant rise from 2017, with SDGs reporting increasing from 39% to 69% for N-100 firms and 43% to 72% for G-250 corporations. Regional differences were noted, with 96% of Japanese companies and 48% of Chinese firms included SDGs in their reports. The automobile sector saw substantial growth, with SDGs reporting rising from 38% in 2017 to 80% in 2020. PwC studies in 2018 and 2019 (Scott & McGill, 2018; Scott & McGill, 2019) showed that 72% of surveyed firms included Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their reporting, with 59% incorporating them into sustainability reports and 51% in annual reports. Only 21% of companies mentioned SDGs in the CEO or Chairman's statement, up from 13% in 2018. Additionally, 65% of companies referred to specific goals.

Nichita et al. (2020b) noted deliberate efforts toward SDGs related to energy (SDGs 07), water (SDGs 06), waste (SDGs 12), carbon emissions (SDGs 13), and employment (SDGs 08). Threlfall et al. (2020) identified SDGs 08, SDGs 13, and SDGs 12 as the most emphasized, while biodiversity goals (SDGs 14 and SDGs 15) were less prioritized by the corporate sector. Nechita et al. (2020) reported over 90% of the companies acknowledged and recognized the importance of SDGs 12, 13, and 17.

Prior studies on SDGs

A few studies that have been conducted on SDGs reporting have been summarized in Table-01.

Table 1. Summary of Previous literature on SDGs

Authors	Context	Major Findings
(Rosati & Faria, 2019a)	Global	Early SDGs reporting is linked to larger firms with more intangible assets, stronger sustainability commitments, more female and younger directors, and external pressures from legal, cultural, and educational systems.
(Czaja-Cieszyńska & Kočański, 2019)-	Central and Eastern Europe	The investigation found that while firms disclose SDGs, reports often lack comparability, external verification, and substance, highlighting the need for more effective communication of corporate social responsibility efforts.
(Rosati & Faria, 2019b)	Global	Organizations reporting on SDGs tend to be in countries with high climate vulnerability, strong CSR, higher education, and lower market coordination, indulgence and individualism, employment protection, and power distance.
(Nichita et al., 2020)	Central and Eastern European countries	In 63% of documents analyzed, corporations didn't specify their SDGs investments, and SDGs reporting varied significantly in structure and scope, even within the same sector.
(Nechita et al., 2020)	Chemical industry of Central and Eastern European countries	Key findings show corporations focus on environmental and decent work-related SDGs, with variations in firm's SDGs scores largely explained by research and development spending and other intangible factors.
(Curtó-Pagès et al., 2021)	Spanish listed companies	Spanish listed corporations show low commitment to sustainability reporting. Adoption of GRI standards or UN Global Compact membership correlates positively with SDGs reporting. Companies publishing integrated reports are more likely to include SDGs compared to those with standalone or annual reports.
(Erin & Bamigboye, 2022)	Africa	Most of the firms show little or no concern to report on SDGs activities.
(Diaz-Sarachaga, 2021)	Spanish firms	Only 36% of Spanish businesses have a 2030 Agenda strategy. Key reporting issues include intangibility, omission of negative effects, low standardization, and lack of comparability and consistency in disclosures.

Authors	Context	Major Findings
(Hummel & Szekely, 2022)	Listed firms of Europe	SDGs reporting quality has improved over time yet lacks quantitative and forward-looking details. SDGs disclosure is influenced by socially responsible investors and environmental pressure, not by financial analysts, workers, or media.
(Pizzi et al., 2021)	Europe	Companies with long-term orientation and balanced environments between indulgence and constraint are more likely to disclose SDGs contributions, while masculinity and individualism hinder SDGs reporting.
(Küçükgül et al., 2022)	Sweden and Netherlands	Corporations often narrate their SDGs commitment, but GRI and IIRC guidelines promote consistent, comparable, and concise SDGs measurement and communication.
(Erin et al., 2022)	Nigeria	Nigerian companies have performed poorly in terms of corporate SDGs. The SDGs cannot be realized overlooking the assistance of corporate entities.

Till now, the evaluation of SDGs reporting practices by the corporate sector of Bangladesh has been largely overlooked by researchers, making it difficult to determine whether Bangladeshi companies are assisting the government in achieving the SDGs within the due time of 2030. Furthermore, there is limited insight into whether the government should take action to enhance these efforts. While DSE-30 listed companies are closely monitored by capital market investors, the strength of their stakeholders in compelling companies to mention contributions to SDGs in their reports remains unclear. This gap in research highlights the need for further investigation into the SDGs reporting practices of DSE-30 companies and the role of stakeholders in encouraging such practices. This study aims to address the existing gap by examining the top-listed companies' SDGs reporting practices in Bangladesh.

Research Methodology

Sample size and Research Method

The research focuses on a sample of firms from the DSE 30 index, spanning various industries: five from each of banking, pharmaceuticals, and fuel & power; four from engineering; three from telecommunications; two from each of food & allied and financial institutions; and one each from insurance, cement, tannery, and other industries. The DSE-30 companies were selected due to their leadership in their respective industries and their comparatively comprehensive reporting practices, particularly in voluntary disclosures related to sustainability and the SDGs, making them suitable for studies on such topics.

Using content analysis alongside the PwC framework, which has been used in the study of Erin & Bamigboye (2022), Erin et al. (2022), and Bebbington & Unerman (2018), the study evaluates corporate compliance with SDGs reporting. The content analysis method, supported by research from Nechita et al. (2020) and Saha & Jannat (2021), effectively converts qualitative data into quantitative measures. For example, if any companies report on any particular SDGs, the company is rewarded 01 for that particular SDGs for a year; otherwise, it will be given 0 (zero). The analysis of this study covers five years (2017-2021), starting from 2017 to allow firms adequate time to understand and assess their contributions to SDGs following their adoption in 2015. The study used secondary data from company websites, the LANKABANGLA financial portal, and annual reports, including directors' and chairman's statements. It analyzed SDGs reporting from 2017 to 2021, covering 30 companies and generating 150 observations over the five-year period.

Then, we have constructed a ranking system based on the companies' contribution to each of SDGs. SDGs that receive greater contributions from top-listed companies are placed in the first position, and other rankings are also produced using the same method. After that, sector-wise contribution is also presented to highlight the sectors that are very much concerned with the attainment of goals of the UN SDGs 2030 agenda.

Findings

Reporting on SDGs by Companies Based on PwC Framework

After reviewing the annual reports of the DSE-30 listed firms in Bangladesh, the authors discover that the SDGs reporting practices of the top listed companies in Bangladesh, as shown in Figure-01, are becoming more prevalent. According to the findings, top-listed firms in Bangladesh are concerned about the sustainable development goals, with over 62% of corporations disclosing SDGs in their annual reports in 2021, up from 33% in 2017. According to the findings, SDGs reporting practice is becoming a growing issue for companies when providing voluntary information.

Figure 1. SDGs in annual report

Figure 2. Separate SDGs report

Furthermore, the authors discover that few companies, as shown in Figure-02, are generating separate reports for SDGs in their annual reports, integrating CSR reporting in the SDGs reporting. In 2017, just 10% of corporations offered separate SDGs reporting

that included their contribution to SDGs accomplishment, rising to 38% in 2021. Furthermore, the authors found that, even though sustainability is an emerging issue in today's globe, the top listed firms of Bangladesh are less concerned with sustainability and SDGs related issues in preparing reports. Only 55% of enterprises, as shown in Figure-03, published a sustainability report in 2021, compared to 50% in 2017. Furthermore, all the firms that prepared separate sustainability reports did not include SDGs in their disclosure, although the majority incorporated SDGs in their sustainability reporting.

Figure 3. Sustainability and SDGs

Figure 4. Prioritization of SDGs

The study of the selected firms' information suggests that companies prioritized (focusing on specific goals) SDGs, as shown in Figure-04, by 13% in 2017, 30% in 2018, 34% in 2019, and 41% in both 2020 and 2021. In response to research objective 01, it can be said that the result of this study demonstrates low compliance, implying that businesses in Bangladesh pay little or no attention to prioritizing SDGs activities and performance. In 2021, less than half of corporations prioritized SDGs meaningful to their stakeholders.

Figure 5. KPI and Measurement approach related to SDGs

Figure-05 demonstrates that 38% of organizations reported SDGs-related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and targets, whereas 21% of firms stated the fundamental measurement approach utilized in SDGs reporting. This might indicate that enterprises are uninformed of the measuring strategy or are unconcerned with measurement since there are no regulatory requirements in this area.

Figure 6. SDGs in business model and Director's report

Figure-06 depicts the firms' proclivity to include SDGs in their corporate strategy and CEO report. In 2021, SDGs were recognized by around 38% of firms while developing their business strategy. This finding shows that most Bangladeshi corporations failed to integrate SDGs into their strategic corporate goals; however, the trend is developing. It was also discovered that 12 corporations, or 41%, addressed SDGs in their CEO/chairman statement. This suggests that most CEOs of the 30 selected firms in Bangladesh aren't committed to the attainment of SDGs. This might be deliberate, since most Bangladeshi enterprises do not have a clear plan for SDGs in their business and corporate strategy. Erin & Bamigboye (2022) also found a similar result in their research conducted upon African companies on the topic of reporting SDGs activities.

The findings of this study indicate that attaining meaningful SDGs disclosure would be almost impossible without the participation of corporate institutions. The power players (CEO, board, and management) of corporate institutions may influence social change within the organization, particularly on concerns of sustainability. According to the results, there seems to be a disconnect between the degree to which boards acknowledge sustainability as a major business problem and their success in evaluating and managing it. In this research, affirming the role of institutional theory emphasizes the necessity of the board's support in developing and implementing a strategy that permits and assures long-term sustainable value generation.

Companies' Contributions, Directly or Indirectly, on Specific SDGs

In response to the second research objective of examining the precise contributions towards individual SDGs, Table 03 presents an overview of the contributions made by

the companies listed in the DSE-30 index towards specific SDGs throughout the period spanning from 2017 to 2021. This table considers both the direct and indirect contributions made by the 30 selected firms. The term "direct contribution" refers to the act of a corporation actively engaging in relevant metrics and reporting them as Sustainable Development Goals. On the other hand, "indirect contribution" signifies that a company has contributed to important indicators, as determined through our study, but has not officially recorded them as SDGs. The final two columns in Table-03 are the Total column and the Rank column, which are determined by ranking the SDGs based on their highest percentage.

Based on the research outcomes, a significant proportion of firms demonstrated a preference for prioritizing SDGs-08, as it is very pertinent to the corporate domain. SDGs 08 holds the top position, boasting a mean score of 94%, denoting the participation of 28 firms on average in fostering both decent work and economic growth. Robi employs health and safety awareness sessions and talent development initiatives to establish and maintain a satisfactory working environment. SDGs 04 (Quality Education) is the second goal that receives significant contributions from most companies. As part of their CSR initiatives, over 81% of companies engage in philanthropic activities by making donations towards the advancement of education. In relation to Sustainable Development Goal 04, the topic of discussion is Robi-10 Minute School in Bangladesh, which offers digital educational services to various places, including urban, semi-urban, and rural regions. Additionally, there are corporations that contribute to the promotion of education by offering scholarships or supporting infrastructure development. SDGs 01 aiming to eradicate poverty, holds the third rank among the other Sustainable Development Goals.

It is noteworthy that around 69% of organizations actively contribute to efforts aimed at reducing poverty. As a contribution towards the achievement of SDGs 01, CITY Bank Limited undertook the philanthropic initiative of donating a total of 82,500 blankets to those experiencing homelessness within the period spanning from 2020 to 2021, with the aim of alleviating poverty. Moreover, amidst the worldwide catastrophe caused by the COVID-19 epidemic, the corporate sector in Bangladesh has played a crucial role in supporting the government's efforts by generously contributing face masks, vaccines, and other essential health-related resources to ensure the well-being and safety of the general population. On average, it has been observed that around 68% of the selected firms provide contributions towards promoting good health and well-being, as outlined in SDGs-03. BEXIMCO PHARMA expressed their commitment to public health by stating, "We provided much-needed personal protective equipment (PPE), N95 masks, goggles, and PCR kits worth US \$2 million." The company provided support for a range of telemedicine programs aimed at enabling physicians to maintain the provision of medical care to their patients. Since its official debut, the company has been offering Bemsivir to government-designated COVID-19 hospitals without any charge. Additionally, the organization has sent free medicines to foreign countries as an act of humanitarian assistance.

The 5th-ranked Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs 10), which emphasizes reducing inequalities, is supported by around 65% of firms that prioritize providing equitable opportunities for all employees. Grameenphone has expressed its dedication to addressing the goals outlined in Sustainable Development Goal 10 (SDGs 10). Specifically, the

company aims to diminish inequities and empower societies through ensuring access to connectivity, digital & technological inclusion, as well as timely social responses and environmental challenges over time. The ambition is to contribute to UN SDGs #10, reduced inequalities, and responsible business practices. Grameenphone is committed to maintaining responsible business practices throughout its entire supply chain, ensuring that its partners maintain the same standards". It is essential that other corporate organizations include this information within their annual reports. In addition, it is indispensable for the organization to furnish data regarding the demographics of its workers, encompassing individuals from diverse backgrounds. Moreover, a significant proportion of enterprises, namely 63%, made contributions towards the achievement of SDGs 17, which focuses on fostering partnerships to attain the universal objectives. A prime example of implications is the collaborative endeavor between the 333-helpline initiative in collaboration with the government's a2i program. Moreover, it is noteworthy that a significant proportion of enterprises, specifically 61%, provide information pertaining to the effective utilization of water resources and water consumption. This disclosure is aimed at aligning with the objectives outlined in SDGs-06, which focuses on the attainment of clean water and sanitation. The phenomenon is elucidated by Robi's water purifying facility, known as "Nirapod Pani Shushtho Jibon (Safe Water, Sound Health)," strategically situated in prominent public areas. According to the survey results, the eighth rank signifies that around 58% of organizations provide disclosure pertaining to the quantification of waste production and their waste management practices, aligning with SDGs 12. For instance, EBL has made a significant contribution towards achieving this Sustainable Development Goals by ensuring that liquid waste is processed using an Effluent Treatment Plant (ETP), while solid trash is appropriately disposed of through an incinerator. The Olympic Industry Ltd. has implemented a strategy to optimize water usage by fully utilizing 100% of the water in their battery manufacture for their battery factories, so achieving a zero effluent production process.

SDGs 07, which pertains to Affordable and Clean Energy, occupies the ninth (9th) position on the list. Based on the findings of the study, it can be observed that a majority of organizations, namely, an average of 56%, have adopted the use of renewable energy. This indicates that 17 out of the total 30 companies surveyed primarily use renewable sources for their energy generation. The action taken by BATBC in response to this issue was reported as follows: "We installed 166 KW solar panels in Dhaka Factory and are now pursuing installations in Green Leaf Threshing Plant, Kushtia, and Savar Factory". The findings of SDGs 05 reveal that 24% of companies acknowledge the importance of addressing issues related to gender equality. Specifically, these companies have identified the significance of equal pay between men and women, ensuring safe working conditions for women, and making contributions towards the empowerment of women in society. The City Bank Ltd., as an illustration, demonstrated a commitment to fostering women's empowerment through the public exhibition of a board composition that included four female members. LankaBangla Finance Limited (LBFL) has revealed their commitment to women empowerment by emphasizing their endeavors to enhance the empowerment of women. To promote female entrepreneurship, LBFL has introduced ANONNYA, a specialized installment loan program for women entrepreneurs. This loan is made available to various industries, such as, printing and packaging, boutique homes, beauty parlors, manufacturing concerns, and trade houses. LBFL aims to empower women through their assistance in these endeavors.

Table 2. Ranking of SDGs based on contribution by the corporate sector of Bangladesh.

Goal	Indicators	No. of companies out of 30 sample firms					Total		Rank
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Number	Percentage	
SDGs-8: Decent Work and Economic Growth	Disclose on the proportion of workers who have permanent employment contracts	28	28	28	28	29	140	94%	1
SDGs-4: Quality Education	Report on the programs carried to support and promote education as part of CSR	23	23	25	26	25	122	81%	2
SDGs-1: No poverty	Disclosure about activities to support poor communities	17	19	21	22	24	103	69%	3
SDGs-3: Good Health and Well-being	Report on the expenditure on public health related issues	16	17	20	23	24	100	67%	4
SDGs-10: Reduced Inequalities	Emphasis on equal opportunities for all employees.	16	17	22	22	23	100	67%	5
SDGs-17: Partnerships for the Goals	Company's investment in multi-stakeholder partnerships.	15	16	20	22	22	95	63%	6
SDGs-6: Clean Water and Sanitation	Report on the efficient usage of water/ water consumption	13	16	20	22	21	92	61%	7
SDGs-12: Responsible Consumption and Production	Disclosure on the amount of waste it produced and the management of those waste	14	18	18	18	19	87	58%	8
SDGs-7: Affordable and Clean Energy	Use of renewable energy	14	16	17	18	19	84	56%	9
SDGs-5: Gender Equality	Report about safe working condition for women and donation for the welfare of the women in the society	13	16	17	18	19	83	55%	10

Goal	Indicators	No. of companies out of 30 sample firms					Total		Rank
		2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Number	Percentage	
SDGs-2: Zero hunger	Effort to end hunger with the help of food campaign or Donation	11	15	17	20	19	82	55%	11
SDGs-13: Climate Action	Reporting on carbon emissions	13	16	17	18	18	82	55%	12
SDGs-11: Sustainable Cities and Communities	Investment in water, sanitation, energy or telecoms with private participation and other sustainable issues for the country	15	16	17	16	17	81	54%	13
SDGs-15: Life on Land	Strategy for managing future risks related to loss of biodiversity resources and tree planting.	14	15	16	14	18	77	51%	14
SDGs-16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions	Company's policy to promote fair business (like corruption prevention and whistleblowing policy)	13	14	15	16	18	76	51%	15
SDGs-9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	Activities to promote the inclusion of SME in their business operations.	8	9	12	15	17	61	41%	16
SDGs-14: Life Below Water	Strategy for managing future risks associated with aquatic ecosystem depletion.	1	1	1	1	2	6	4%	17

The LankaBangla Shikha Platform has formulated and organized a program to distribute bicycles to economically disadvantaged female students, with the aim of enhancing their educational experience by providing them with a means of transportation to school.

SDGs-02 (zero hunger) holds the eleventh position in the list of contributions. Approximately 55% of the companies actively contribute to the goal of alleviating hunger. BRAC Bank Limited reported their philanthropic endeavors as "Provision of food assistance to 30,267 families affected by the Covid-19 pandemic" to mitigate food insecurity. The outcome of Sustainable Development Goal 13, which focuses on climate action, illustrates the growing efficacy of enterprises in Bangladesh addressing issues related to climate change. On average, approximately 55% of corporations disclose carbon emissions in their corporate reports. BATB Company Ltd. has made a significant contribution towards the achievement of SDGs 13. This was accomplished through their explicit declaration, whereby they said that they had successfully mitigated carbon emissions by a substantial amount of 3,700 tons since the year 2017. This remarkable achievement was made possible through the implementation of several energy-saving efforts. Furthermore, IDLC Ltd. upholds green office practices & Green Banking activities to address the issue of climate action. The SDGs-11 on Sustainable Cities and Communities, which holds the 13th position in the overall ranking, reveals that 54% of firms allocate investments towards water, sanitation, energy, technology, telecommunications, and other sustainable concerns through private sector engagement for the betterment of the nation. The provision of extended financial help by City Bank Ltd. bank for technological improvements at the Detective Branch of Dhaka Metropolitan Police serves as an illustrative instance of the implementation of SDGs 11.

Based on the findings of Sustainable Development Goal 15 (Life on Land), it is evident that around 52% of firms have identified a strategic approach to mitigate potential risks associated with the loss of biodiversity resources and the establishment of tree plantations. For instance, BSRM (Steel Rerolling Mill) had undertaken the initiative of planting 15,000 trees within its factory premises. A collaborative initiative has been initiated by BSRM to address reforestation efforts in conjunction with partner organizations, focusing on conducting tree plantation programs in the vicinity of major steel factories. Likewise, the outcome conformed to expectations for SDGs-16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions), as an average of 15 companies acknowledged their commitment to promoting equitable business practices. According to a statement from LankaBangla Finance Limited, corruption in the financial services sector manifests in several forms such as money laundering, rate-rigging, and tax evasion. These illicit activities have detrimental effects on public trust in financial institutions. The Code of Conduct of LBFL emphasizes the company's strict stance of zero tolerance against the acceptance or provision of bribes in any manner. According to the Sustainable Development Goal 09 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), approximately 42% of firms provide reports on their initiatives aimed at facilitating the involvement of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in their organizational activities as part of SDGs 09 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure). IDLC is committed to implementing sustainable banking practices, including green banking, project financing, and product development, to effectively contribute to the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 09. 'Life Below Water' (SDGs 14) is listed at the lowest level, since only 4% of firms have disclosed details regarding their strategies aimed at addressing the prospective risk associated to the depletion of aquatic ecosystems. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that SDGs-8,

SDGs-4, SDGs-1, SDGs-3, and SDGs-10 receive more attention from the corporate organization where SDGs-14 is greatly overlooked due to a lack of opportunity for companies to promote it.

Sector wise Contributions on particular SDGs

Different industries can contribute uniquely to various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). For example, one sector might focus on SDGs 05, while another targets SDGs 08. This study examined each industry of the DSE 30 index to assess their contributions to the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. It aimed to analyze each sector's relative importance and alignment with specific SDGs, revealing unique sector-specific approaches and emphasis on various sustainability objectives to fulfill the 3rd research objectives of this study. The analysis first examined individual firms' contributions to each of the 17 SDGs, then summarized the findings by sector, and finally used the average SDGs scores to identify the sector contributing most to SDGs attainment.

Financial Institutions' Leading Role

Financial institutions have exhibited a significant dedication to Sustainable Development Goals, which can be attributed to their proximity and intrinsic alignment with the broader population. The financial sector, specifically the companies listed under the DSE 30 index, has shown a greater level of contribution towards nearly all Sustainable Development Goals in comparison to other sectors within the same index. It is worth noting that financial institutions have made significant contributions to all Sustainable Development Goals except for SDGs 14. Approximately 92% of the leading financial institutions concentrate on the attainment of the SDGs.

The Strategic Position of Banks

Banks have achieved a significant standing in terms of their contributions towards the Sustainable Development Goals, with an average of 87% of top-listed banks collaborating closely with governments to support the attainment of these goals. The findings from table 04 indicate that a significant proportion, ranging from approximately 90% to 100%, of the leading banks included under the DSE 30 index actively contribute towards achieving SDGs-3, SDGs-4, SDGs-6, SDGs-7, SDGs-8, SDGs -9, SDGs-10, SDGs-11, SDGs-15, SDGs-16, and SDGs-17. Additionally, a noteworthy percentage, ranging from 80% to 90% of these banks contribute towards SDGs-1, SDGs -2, SDGs -12, and SDGs-13. Therefore, the bank's significant contributions encompass a wide range of Sustainable Development Goals, however, it is worth noting that SDGs 14 is noticeably absent from the bank's initiatives.

Notable Contributions by Food Sector

Among the sectors of DSE 30 listed firms, the food sector has emerged as the third most significant contributor to the Sustainable Development Goals. Although the sector has made notable contributions, there exist certain areas, namely, SDGs-5, SDGs- 10, SDGs- 14, and SDGs- 16, where there is room for improvement. Around 85% of the leading food corporations concentrate on addressing SDGs concerns.

Table 3. Detailed Sector-wise Contribution to SDGs.

SDGs No.	Goal	Index	Banks	Fuel & Power	Pharmaceuticals	Engineering	Telecommunications	Food & Allied	Financial Institutions	Other
1	No poverty	Disclosure about activities to support poor communities	84%	60%	60%	60%	80%	100%	90%	45%
2	Zero hunger	Effort to end hunger with the help of food campaign or Donation	88%	36%	44%	35%	67%	100%	90%	20%
3	Good health and well being	Report on the expenditure on public health related issues	100%	48%	80%	50%	67%	100%	90%	20%
4	Quality education	Report on the programs carried to support and promote education as part of CSR	100%	96%	76%	60%	100%	100%	100%	35%
5	Gender Equality	Report about safe working condition for women and donation for the welfare of the women in the society	76%	20%	44%	60%	93%	50%	100%	35%
6	Clean water and sanitation	Report on the efficient usage of water/ water consumption	96%	36%	64%	35%	73%	100%	100%	25%
7	Affordable and clean energy	Use of renewable energy	92%	52%	16%	45%	67%	100%	100%	25%

8	Decent work and economic growth	Disclose on the proportion of workers who have permanent employment contracts	100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	80%
9	Industry, innovation and infrastructure	Activities to promote the inclusion of SME in their business operations.	100%	52%	8%	5%	40%	10%	100%	15%
10	Reducing inequalities	Emphasis on equal opportunities for all employees.	100%	60%	48%	60%	100%	80%	100%	15%
11	Sustainable cities and communities	Investment in water, sanitation, energy or telecoms with private participation and other sustainable issues for the country	96%	24%	44%	25%	67%	100%	100%	25%
12	Responsible consumption and production	Disclosure on the amount of waste it produced and the management of those waste	80%	32%	56%	55%	60%	100%	100%	25%
13	Climate Action	Reporting on carbon emissions	80%	48%	28%	40%	67%	100%	100%	25%
14	Life below water	Strategy for managing future risks associated with aquatic ecosystem depletion.	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	50%	10%	0%
15	Life on land	Strategy for managing future risks related to loss of biodiversity resources and tree planting.	96%	28%	48%	50%	0%	100%	90%	25%
16	Peace, justice, and strong institutions	Company's policy to promote fair business (like corruption prevention and whistleblowing policy)	92%	24%	48%	20%	67%	60%	100%	25%
17	Partnership for the goals	Company's investment in multi-stakeholder partnerships.	92%	32%	56%	65%	80%	100%	100%	25%
Average			87%	44%	48%	44%	66%	85%	92%	27%
Position			2 nd	6 th	5 th	6 th	4 th	3 rd	1 st	7 th

The Noteworthy Involvement of the Telecommunications Sector

The telecommunications sector demonstrates a noteworthy role in contributing to the SDGs, specifically in SDGs 04, 05, 08, and 10, with an average contribution of 66%. Thus, the communications sector is not falling behind in terms of its contribution to the Sustainable Development Goals. More than 90% of the leading telecommunication firms have included the goals outlined in SDGs-4, SDGs-5, SDGs -8, and SDGs -10. Around 70% to 90% of the leading banks prioritize (focusing on specific SDGs) their efforts towards achieving SDGs-1, SDGs-6, and SDGs- 17. Additionally, a range of 60% to 70% of firms actively contribute to SDGs -2, SDGs- 3, SDGs-7, SDGs-11, SDGs- 12, SDGs-13, and SDGs- 16. Based on the available data, it is possible to assert that the telecommunication industry occupies a position that is likely to be ranked fourth.

The Position and Challenges of the Pharmaceutical Industry

Pharmaceutical companies are ranked sixth in terms of their adherence to the 2030 agenda, with just 48% of them reporting on related issues. However, challenges occur in the area of waste management. Although making substantial contributions to SDGs- 08, SDGs- 03, and SDGs- 04, there is an observable failure to make progress towards SDGs-07 and SDGs- 09, indicating the need for enhanced focus and attention.

But the contribution of the pharmaceutical industry is not as substantial as anticipated. Ultimately, it achieved the fifth position. Pharmaceutical firms engage in the utilization of chemicals, necessitating their obligation to provide transparency on the handling and disposal of those toxic waste chemicals. But approximately 56% of the leading pharmaceutical companies provide reports on waste management, but 80% of the top-listed banks and 100% of the top-listed financial institutions address this matter in their reports. Nevertheless, it is evident that leading pharmaceutical corporations prioritize their contributions towards SDGs- 08, SDGs- 03, and SDGs- 04, while allocating comparatively fewer resources towards other SDGs. However, their contribution to SDGs- 07 and SDGs- 09 is very limited in comparison to other industries. Only 16% and 5% of top-listed pharmaceutical companies contribute towards achieving SDGs- 07 and SDGs- 09 respectively.

The Contribution of the Fuel & Power and the Engineering Sectors

The fuel and power industry, as well as the engineering sector, are two significant domains that play a crucial role in several aspects of society. While there is an anticipation from power sector and engineering sector organizations to prioritize renewable energy, it is noteworthy that just 52% of power companies and 45% of engineering enterprises have adopted renewable energy sources. In contrast, it is anticipated that these two industries ought to make a more substantial contribution, particularly regarding Sustainable Development Goal 13, as they possess significant impact over carbon emissions. However, it is worth mentioning that only 48% of the leading power companies and 40% of the leading engineering firms currently disclose information on their carbon emissions. A small proportion, ranging from 55% to 65% of the leading engineering companies actively engage with SDGs- 01, SDGs- 04, SDGs- 05, SDGs- 10, SDGs- 12, and SDGs-

17. On the other hand, more than 80 percent of power firms actively contribute to SDGs-04 and SDGs-08.

Conclusions

Companies are interested in ensuring the 2030 Agenda, because they cannot prosper in a world of poverty, inequality, insecurity, and environmental stress. Many global firms are now reporting their SDGs contributions, with 72% incorporating SDGs in their reporting according to Scott & McGill (2019) and SDGs concern is also increased among Japanese firms noted by Threlfall et al. (2020). This study is conducted to answer three questions: Are the top listed companies in Bangladesh concerned with sustainable development goals? To which SDGs, top performing companies are contributing most? and Which industry is contributing more on each SDGs? Using the DSE-30 listed companies as a sample, the study analyzed secondary data from 2017 to 2021, guided by legitimacy, stakeholder, and institutional theories.

In response to the first research question, it is found that 62% of companies in 2021 mentioned the term SDGs in their annual report, while 38% of companies prepared separate reports containing the company's contribution to the each of SDGs. Additionally, only 41% of organizations explicitly prioritized (focuses on the attainment of specific goals) SDGs relevant to their activities in 2021, with 38% mentioning SDGs in their business model. The findings also show that major Bangladeshi companies are increasingly enhancing their SDGs reporting practices, but at a relatively slow rate.

To address the second research question, companies' direct or indirect contributions to particular SDGs are evaluated. The results indicate that most corporations are concentrating on achieving SDGs-08 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), which is very relevant to the corporate sector. Also, companies provide greater support and effort into the achievement of SDGs-04 (Quality Education), SDGs-01 (No Poverty/Poverty reduction), SDGs-03 (Good Health and Well-being), and SDGs-10 (Reduced Inequalities), while devoting less effort to the attainment of SDGs-14, SDGs-09, SDGs-16, SDGs-15.

The third research question is addressed by presenting sector wise contribution on each of SDGs and highlighting the sector which exerts greater emphasize on SDGs. The result suggests that Financial Institutions, Banks, and Food & Allied sectors are the top three sectors, with an average score of 92%, 87%, and 85%, which are concern with the fulfillment of the SDGs 2030 agenda. It is also found that only 56% top listed pharmaceuticals companies report on waste management though they work with chemical products which produce toxic waste. The Fuel & Power and Engineering sectors are supposed to be serious with the use of renewable energy (SDGs-07) and carbon emissions (SDGs-13). But only 52% top listed power companies and 45% leading engineering companies use renewable energy, while 48% power companies and 40% top engineering companies report on carbon emissions.

The findings indicate that the leading listed companies in Bangladesh are not yet significantly focused on achieving the SDGs by 2030. This raises concerns about the situation of other listed and unlisted companies. If this trend continues, Bangladesh could

become one of the lowest performers in SDGs attainment compared to other nations. To improve SDGs reporting in Bangladesh, regulators should mandate that corporations must disclose their contributions to the SDGs, following the example of developed countries. Policymakers must foster a culture of accountability and transparency in policymaking to ensure SDGs attainment. The government should develop mechanisms to evaluate corporate contributions to SDGs and provide incentives to those companies that perform well on those evaluation mechanisms. Conversely, companies failing to meet minimum scores should face penalties, such as additional taxes.

The research faces limitations due to its small sample size and potential subjectivity in content analysis, which can introduce biases. Additionally, the results of this study are specific to the selected companies in Bangladesh and, therefore, cannot be generalized to other sectors within the country or to different geographical contexts. The findings may not fully represent the broader corporate landscape, particularly in terms of varying industries or company sizes. Future research could expand the sample size to enhance generalizability. Comparative studies between Bangladesh and other developing countries, particularly in South Asia, would provide valuable insights into regional trends in SDGs reporting. Further, examining the factors that influence SDGs reporting could offer a deeper understanding of what drives or hinders corporate contributions to SDGs. Longitudinal studies could also be useful in tracking changes in SDGs reporting practices over time.

References

- Alam, S. (2016). *Millennium Development Goals: End-period stocktaking and final evaluation report*. Bangladesh Planning Commission.
https://plancomm.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/plancomm.portal.gov.bd/files/4e4ab41c_e818_4019_bebe_9d64282a6513/MDG%20Final%20Evaluation%20Report%202016.pdf
- Bebbington, J., & Unerman, J. (2018). Achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals: An enabling role for accounting research. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 31(1), 2–24.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/AAAJ-06-2017-2954>
- Biggeri, M., Clark, D. A., Ferrannini, A., & Mauro, V. (2019). Tracking the SDGs in an ‘integrated’ manner: A proposal for a new index to capture synergies and trade-offs between and within goals. *World Development*, 122, 628–647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2019.05.022>
- Curtó-Pagès, F., Ortega-Rivera, E., Castellón-Durán, M., & Jané-Llopis, E. (2021). Coming in from the cold: A longitudinal analysis of SDG reporting practices by Spanish listed companies since the approval of the 2030 agenda. *Sustainability*, 13(3), Article 1178.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031178>

- Czaja-Cieszyńska, H., & Kocharński, K. (2019). Sustainable development reporting of selected socially responsible listed companies. *Zeszyty Teoretyczne Rachunkowości*, 60(132), 93–100. <https://doi.org/10.17402/376>
- Deegan, C. (2002). Introduction: The legitimising effect of social and environmental disclosures – A theoretical exploration. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 15(3), 282–311. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513570210435852>
- Diaz-Sarachaga, J. M. (2021). Shortcomings in reporting contributions towards the sustainable development goals. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(4), 1261–1272. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2124>
- Erin, O. A., & Bamigboye, O. A. (2022). Evaluation and analysis of SDG reporting: Evidence from Africa. *Journal of Accounting and Organizational Change*, 18(3), 369–396. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAOC-02-2020-0025>
- Erin, O. A., Bamigboye, O. A., & Oyewo, B. (2022). Sustainable development goals (SDG) reporting: An analysis of disclosure. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 12(5), 761–789. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAEE-02-2020-0037>
- Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic management: A stakeholder approach*. Pitman.
- Herzig, C., & Schaltegger, S. (2011). Corporate sustainability reporting. In J. Godemann & G. Michelsen (Eds.), *Sustainability communication: Interdisciplinary perspectives and theoretical foundations* (pp. 151–169). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-1697-1_14
- Hummel, K., & Szekely, M. (2022). Disclosure on the Sustainable Development Goals—Evidence from Europe. *Accounting in Europe*, 19(1), 152–189. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17449480.2021.1894347>
- Kingo, L., & Mohin, T. (2018). *Integrating the SDGs into corporate reporting: A practical guide*. United Nations Global Compact. <https://www.unglobalcompact.org/library/5628>
- Kücükgül, E., Cerin, P., & Liu, Y. (2022). Enhancing the value of corporate sustainability: An approach for aligning multiple SDGs guides on reporting. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 333, Article 130005. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.130005>
- Masud, M. A. K., & Hossain, M. S. (2012). Corporate social responsibility reporting practices in Bangladesh: A study of selected private commercial

- banks. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 6(2), 42–47.
<http://www.iosrjournals.org>
- Masum, M. H., Hasan, M. T., Tuhin, M. K., & Chowdhury, Y. (2020). Factors affecting the sustainability reporting: Evidence from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development*, 10(3), 8323–8338.
<https://doi.org/10.24247/ijmperdjun2020792>
- Mohin, T., Reynolds, F., & Kingo, L. (2018). *In focus: Addressing investor needs in business reporting on the SDGs*. Global Reporting Initiative.
<https://www.globalreporting.org/media/sphmq4r0/addressing-investor-needs-sdgs-reporting.pdf>
- Nechita, E., Manea, C. L., Nichita, E. M., Irimescu, A. M., & Manea, D. (2020). Is financial information influencing the reporting on SDGs? Empirical evidence from Central and Eastern European chemical companies. *Sustainability*, 12(21), Article 9251. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219251>
- Nichita, E.-M., Nechita, E., Manea, C.-L., Manea, D., & Irimescu, A.-M. (2020). Reporting on Sustainable Development Goals: A score-based approach with company-level evidence from Central-Eastern Europe economies. *Journal of Accounting and Management Information Systems*, 19(3), 489–521.
<https://doi.org/10.24818/jamis.2020.03004>
- Perello-Marin, M. R., Rodríguez-Rodríguez, R., & Alfaro-Saiz, J. J. (2022). Analysing GRI reports for the disclosure of SDG contribution in European car manufacturers. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 181, Article 121744. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121744>
- Pizzi, S., Del Baldo, M., Caputo, F., & Venturelli, A. (2022). Voluntary disclosure of Sustainable Development Goals in mandatory non-financial reports: The moderating role of cultural dimension. *Journal of International Financial Management and Accounting*, 33(1), 83–106.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jifm.12139>
- Pizzi, S., Rosati, F., & Venturelli, A. (2021). The determinants of business contribution to the 2030 Agenda: Introducing the SDG Reporting Score. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(1), 404–421.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2628>
- Raquiba, H., & Ishak, Z. (2020). Sustainability reporting practices in the energy sector of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 10(1), 508–516. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijeep.8621>

- Rosati, F., & Faria, L. G. D. (2019a). Addressing the SDGs in sustainability reports: The relationship with institutional factors. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 215, 1312–1326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.107>
- Rosati, F., & Faria, L. G. D. (2019b). Business contribution to the Sustainable Development Agenda: Organizational factors related to early adoption of SDG reporting. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 26(3), 588–597. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1705>
- Saha, T., & Jannat, F. (2021). Disclosure of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in Bangladesh: A study on DSE listed companies. *Asian Business Review*, 11(3), 93–100. <https://doi.org/10.18034/abr.v11i3.594>
- Scott, L., & McGill, A. (2018). *From promise to reality: Does business really care about the SDGs?* PwC. <http://www.pwc.com/sdgreportingchallenge>
- Scott, L., & McGill, A. (2019). *Creating a strategy for a better world: How the Sustainable Development Goals can provide the framework for business to deliver progress on our global challenges.* PwC. <https://www.pwc.co.uk/who-we-are/our-purpose/strategy/sustainable-development-goals.html>
- Suchman, M. C. (1995). Managing legitimacy: Strategic and institutional approaches. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(3), 571–610. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258789>
- Threlfall, R., King, A., Shulman, J., & Bartels, W. (2020). *The time has come: The KPMG survey of sustainability reporting 2020.* KPMG. <https://kpmg.com/ua/en/home/insights/2021/01/the-time-has-come-survey-of-sustainability-reporting.html>
- Whittingham, K. L., Earle, A. G., Leyva-de la Hiz, D. I., & Argiolas, A. (2023). The impact of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals on corporate sustainability reporting. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 26(1), 45–61. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23409444221085585>
- World Bank Group. (2022). *GDP growth (annual %) - Bangladesh.* <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG?locations=BD>

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